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Paper-8

Mathematics is the Key to all Fun

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Abstract

Mathematics is a living and growing organism, useful with daily life. It provides enormous opportunities to open our mind for new ideas, providing grey matter pleasure. Mathematics is an analeptic for mind, as it develops the creative thinking and analytic attitude. It makes a person to think immensely. It is felt that teaching of mathematics is not just limited to the transfer of knowledge from the teacher to the student, but it is little more of sharing the enthusiasm and excitement of learning. It has become compulsory to shift from “Chalk and Talk” method to “Child-Centered”, “Indoor Method” to “Outdoor Method” and from “Teaching Mathematics” to “Learning Mathematics”. However, usually mathematics is considered as a dull and boring subject. Students try to escape from learning Mathematics, as they are afraid of the subject and have a very poor interest and attitude towards it. Nevertheless, attitude and interest in a subject plays an important role for scoring achievements in the subject. This theorem will help students and people to change their attitude towards Mathematics. In addition, they will find Mathematics to be the key to all fun.

Introduction-

Learning mathematics is not only a cognitive challenge, but also an affective one. Affect plays a significant role in mathematics learning and instruction and there are three categories of affect related to mathematics learning: beliefs, attitudes, and emotions (McLeod, 1992). Attitude is either a positive or a negative emotional

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disposition towards Mathematics (Haladyna et al., 1983). Attitude is a liking or disliking of Mathematics, a tendency to engage in or avoid mathematical activities, a belief that one is good or bad at mathematics and a belief that mathematics is useful or useless. Students' success in Mathematics depends upon attitude towards mathematics (Farooq and Shah, 2008). Even earlier researched has proved the fact. The attitude of the students towards mathematics and mathematical games was more positive than when the traditional method was used in teaching mathematics. (Alamina and Olubunmi, 2007). There is significant relationship between attitude (patience, confidence and willingness) towards problem solving and mathematics achievement (Norhatta, Tengku and Ismail, 2011). Interest in mathematics could be regarded a predictor for mathematics achievement (Heinze, Reiss, Franziska, 2005).

Importance of Mathematics cannot be limited to the single aspect of life. No aspect of life is left untouched by Mathematics. In the words of Bertrand Russell, "What is best in mathematics deserves not merely to be learned as a task but to be assimilated as a part of daily thought and brought again and again before the mind with ever-renewed encouragement." Johnathan David Farley and Orono, Me quoted "You do not study mathematics because it helps you build a bridge. You study mathematics because it is the poetry of the universe. Its beauty transcends mere things." Now the question arises what is Mathematics. The answer lies in some famous quotes: "Mathematics is a game played according to certain rules with meaningless marks on paper": David Hilbert. Galileo has rightly said, "Mathematics is the language with which God wrote the universe."

"The essence of mathematics lies in its freedom."

Georg Cantor -

Mathematics learning can be made effective and interesting by selecting, collecting and using a series of materials and examples from daily life and by realizing the importance and beauty of Mathematics. These materials include riddles, games in newspapers, cards, toys etc. Use of such type of materials helps the students to understand the concepts more easily, effectively, interestingly and clearly in participatory way. This technique at the beginners' level will not only inculcate the positive attitude towards Mathematics but it will form a sound foundation for the learning of advance concepts of Mathematics. Schooling is an extension of home experiences for development. So, one of the main objectives of education at primary stage is to provide the essential requisites motivation, interest and will to learn. Children learn on his own, not just to acquire the knowledge. This is an attempt to improve the present classroom transaction where learners are often with inbuilt fear psychosis towards mathematics learning. Once the positive attitude, interest and will to learn Mathematics is aroused, more than the half of the battle will be won. This present article is an endeavour in this direction. This theorem will help students and people to change their attitude towards Mathematics. In addition, they will find Mathematics to be the key to all fun.

Objectives-

The main objective of this paper is to simplify the mathematics learning by participatory approach that will develop positive attitude, interest and will to learn Mathematics, which in turn will boost the understanding, observation and critical thinking of the students. It will add to their communication skill too. Major objectives of the present theorem are as follows:

1. To create interest of students in Mathematics.
2. To develop positive attitude towards Mathematics.

3. To arouse will to learn Mathematics.
4. To make mathematics easy, enjoyable and activity based.
5. To provide opportunities to learn Mathematics from day-to-day activities and experimentation.
6. To make maximum participation of students as the centre of learning.
7. To make learning a long time stable.
8. To provide opportunities to inculcate learning attitude with emphasis on self-learning.

Methodology-

Marvelous Math-

How fast does a New York taxi go?

What size is grandpa's attic?

How old is the oldest dinosaur?

The answer's in *Mathematics!*

How many seconds in an hour?

How many hours in a day?

What size are the planets in the sky?

How far to the Milky Way?

How fast does lightning travel?

How slow do feathers fall?

How many miles to Istanbul?

***Mathematics* knows it all!**

By: Rebecca Kai Dotlich

Given: Mathematics as a fun –Does it sound odd to you? How a subject that is considered tough and boring can create a fun. Mathematics and Fun: How it is possible? I have never thought of it.

To Prove: *“Mathematics is the key to all Funs.”*

Proof: This phenomenon is nothing but the illusion in your mind generated because of the fact that you have never taken the study of Mathematics for Fun, Play and Enjoyment. But my dear friend

“Mathematics is the key to all Funs.”

“Yes”, it is right. This can be proved with the help of following Mathmagics.

As soon as you finish reading and enjoying this article, you shall definitely say this. Try the following and learn mathematics with fun and enjoyment:

1. **Complete My Magic Box:** Prepare magic square of different sizes (3×3, 5×5, 7×7, 9×9 etc.) in such a way that sum of digits row wise and column wise remains same. Mark these magic squares on a drawing sheet by leaving some of the boxes (red digits) blank as shown in the one below. (Get the sheet laminated, if you want to use it.)

47	58	69	80	01	12	23	34	45
57	68	79	09	11	22	33	44	46
67	78	08	10	21	32	43	54	56
77	07	18	20	31	42	53	55	66
06	17	19	30	41	52	63	65	76
16	27	29	40	51	62	64	75	05
26	28	39	50	61	72	74	04	15
36	38	49	60	71	73	03	14	25
37	48	59	70	81	02	13	24	35

Now ask your friends to fill the blank boxes and enjoy.

Objective: To make little stars to practice the operations of addition and subtraction on natural numbers.

2. **MakeMe:** Draw a geometrical figure on a card-board and cut the figure into pieces as shown below:

Ask your friends to join the pieces to form the geometrical figure.

Objective:

- 1) To develop accuracy and preciseness in drawing geometrical figures.
- 2) To give better conception of geometrical figures.
3. **My Magic Number (AbrakaDabra):** Ask your friend to do the following steps (step1 to step7) one by one and show the magic to your friends.

Step1 Think an Abra Number (Any 2-digit Number e.g. 12).

Step2 Multiply Abra Number by 2 (24).

Step3 Add 8 to it (32).

Step4 Divide it by 4 and get the DabraNumber (8).

Step5 Half the New Abra Number (6).

Step6 Now subtract New Abra Number from Dabra Number (8-6)

Step7 Now tell your friend confidently the answer is 2

The magic lies in this is that every time you perform the above steps with any 2-digit number, the answer remains the same i.e. 2

Objective: To practice algebraic operations multiplication, division, addition, subtraction.

Smart

My dad have me one dollar bill
"Cause I'm his smartest son,
And I swapped it for two shiny quarters
"Cause two is more than one!

And then I took the quarters
and traded them to Lou
For three dimes--I guess he don't know
That three is more than two!

Just then, along came old blind Bates
And just 'cause he can't see
He gave me four nickels for my three dimes,
And four is more than three!

And I took the nickels to Hiram Coombs
Down at the seed-feed store,
And the fool gave me five pennies for them,
And five is more than four!

And then I went and showed my dad,
And he got red in the cheeks

And closed his eyes and shook his head-
Too proud of me to speak!

By: Shel Silverstein

4. **Clock and Angles:** Have you ever seen the wall-clock or wristwatch making different types of angles by their arms (minute arm and hour arm)?

No! Hurriedly go and see.

If it reads 3:00, then what is the angle between the minute arm and hour arm?

Solution: 90°

Objective: To enable the learner to differentiate between the two types of angles.

5. **Mysterious Triangle Area:** The second triangle is formed by rearranging pieces used to create the first. Yet there is a strange gap in the second triangle. Has area vanished? Is the conservation of matter bogus? Explain this paradox.

Hint: “Believe nothing, no matter where you read it or who said it, no matter if I have said it, unless it agrees with your own reason and your common sense.”

– Buddha

Objective: To make the concept of area more comprehensible.

6. **SMARTER THAN MENSA:** Mensa said that he is smartest. If you are smarter than Mensa then answer his following puzzle:-

One of the figures below lacks a characteristic common to the other figures. Which one and why?

Objective: To enable students to identify the difference between two figures.

7. *Just Like Me*: I am a right angled triangle with sides 40, 42, 58. Find two or more right angled triangles just like me i.e. having the same area that I have.

✧ Solution: The triangles with sides:

- 40,42,58
- 24,70,74
- 15,112,113

Objective: To make the concept of area of a right triangle more clear and understandable.

8. *Draw Me*: Draw the figure shown without lifting your pencil from the paper, without retracing any edge and without crossing your own path. How many such paths are possible?

✧

✧ Solution

✧

✧ *There are a total twelve ways of tracing the figure.*

Objective: To make “little stars” to practice and draw figures with fun.

9. **DOUBLET:** Make a "word ladder" from *FOUR* to *FIVE*. Every step in a word ladder differs from the previous step in exactly one letter and each step in the ladder is an English word.

✧ *Solution*

FOUR
FOUL
FOOL
FOOT
FORT
FORE
FIRE
FIVE

Objective: To arouse interest and enthusiasm of little stars for numbers.

10. *Arrange the Cakes:* Move exactly four of the cakes shown to make five rows with four cakes in each row.

✧ Solution:

Objective: To make little stars to practice the arrangement of objects using mathematical rules.

Conclusion

Want to read more, **WHY?** Have you enjoyed the article?

We can guess the answer, it is “Yes”.

Now you can say, “I have learnt Mathematics with Fun.” You can also enjoy Mathematics Quiz, Antakshri, Dum-Shrarj of Mathematical symbols, figures, concepts etc. with your friends.

Hence it has been proved that Mathematics is a Fun. Need is just to realize and correlate it with life and see the magic lying in it. And you will also quote to your friends:-

“Mathematics is the key to all Funs.”

References-

- **Farooq, Muhammad Shahid and Shah, Syed Zia Ullah** (2008). Students' Attitude Towards Mathematics , *Pakistan Economic and Social Review*, 46(1), pp. 75-83 Retrieved from <http://pu.edu.pk/images/journal/pesr/PDF-FILES/5%20FAR%20OOQ%20Students%20Attitude.pdf> on April 15, 2013
- **Alamina, J. I. and Olubunmi, A. Mercy** (2007) Effect of Mathematical Games on Nigerian Students' Attitude towards Mathematics in Secondary Schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis, *The African Symposium*, 7(2), pp. 159-165. Retrieved from <http://www.ncsu.edu/aern/TAS7.2/TAS7.2.pdf> on May 22, 2013.
- **Heinze, Aiso; Reiss, Kristina and Franziska, Rudolph** (2005). Mathematics achievement and interest in mathematics from a differential perspective, *ZDM*, 37 (3). Retrieved from <http://subs.emis.de/journals/ZDM/zdm053a11.pdf> on June 07, 2013

- **Norhatta, Mohd; Tengku, Farah Petri Mahmoodand Ismail, MohdNazri**(2011). Factors that Influence Students in Mathematics Achievement, *International Journal of Academic Research*, 3(3).pp. 49-54.
- **McLeod, D.** (1992). Research on Affect in Mathematics Education: A Reconceptualization of Research on Mathematics Teaching and Learning. Retrieved from <http://www.peterliljedahl.com/wp-content/uploads/Affect-McLeod.pdf> on March 19, 2013.
- **Haladyna, T.; Shaughnessy, J.and Shaughnessy, M.** (1983). A Causal Analysis of Attitude toward Mathematics,*Journal for Research in Mathematics Education*, 14(1), pp. 19-29. Retrieved from <http://www.jstor.org/stable/10.2307/748794>.
